

Figures for the XMM-LSS Field

Figure 1. Corresponding to Fig. 5 in the main paper.

Figure 2. Corresponding to Fig. 6 in the main paper.

Figure 3. Corresponding to Fig. 7 in the main paper.

Figure 4. Corresponding to Fig. 8 in the main paper.

Figure 5. Corresponding to Fig. 10 in the main paper.

Figure 6. Corresponding to Fig. 11 in the main paper.

Figure 9. Corresponding to Fig. 17 in the main paper. The track formed by the colored large points above the quenching locus is constituted of sources with large photo- z s (≥ 4). Generally, such high photo- z s may be unreliable and should be considered with extra caution.

Figure 7. Corresponding to Fig. 12 in the main paper.

Figure 8. Corresponding to Fig. 16 in the main paper.

Figure 10. Corresponding to Fig. 18 in the main paper.

Figure 11. Corresponding to Fig. 19 in the main paper.

Figure 12. Corresponding to Fig. 20 in the main paper.

Figure 13. Corresponding to Fig. 21 in the main paper.

Figure 14. Corresponding to Fig. 22 in the main paper.

Figure 15. Corresponding to Fig. 30 in the main paper. The number of good bands drops below 10 at i -band magnitude of 24.8, which is slightly fainter than that for W-CDF-S (≈ 24). About 50% of our sources are brighter than this nominal depth.

Figure 16. Corresponding to Fig. 31 in the main paper.